

Direct Recording of Intracellular Potentials of Cardiomyocytes Through Solution Processed Planar Electrolyte-Gated Field-Effect Transistors

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Abstract— Minimally invasive recording of intracellular action potentials in electrogenic cells is in high demand. Present tools and technology include invasive patch clamp technique, 3D nanostructures often combined with electro/opto poration methods and nanodevices such as nanowire field-effect transistors. However, these approaches mostly require complex manufacturing processes or are invasive. With the aim of enabling a cost-effective, non-invasive recording platform based on devices that can be easily fabricated and processed from solution with large-area printing techniques, we propose planar Electrolyte Gated Field-Effect Transistors (EGFETs) based on solution-processed carbon based material. Remarkably, despite the planar geometry of the device, we could demonstrate the spontaneous recording of intracellular action potentials of human induced pluripotent stem cells derived cardiomyocytes. The simplicity of the device combined with the high signal to noise ratio opens up new opportunities for low-cost, reliable, and flexible biosensors and arrays for high quality parallel recording of cellular action potentials.

Keywords—Action Potential, Bioelectronics, electrolyte gated field effect transistors, cardiomyocyte

I. INTRODUCTION

Relevant information related to the physiological state of the cell can be obtained from the shape, duration and frequency of the recorded Action Potential (AP) of electrogenic cells [1]. To this end, the development of new tools to accurately record the electrical signals of cells in a minimally/non-invasive way has been the key goal of electrophysiologist. For accurate recording of the AP, the patch clamp technique has been the gold standard method used in electrophysiology for investigating cell activity and for drug testing [2]. However, this technique has many drawbacks including invasiveness, scalability and viability of the cell after recording. In the recent years there has been an enormous effort in proposing new recording platforms that would have high throughput parallel recording in a minimally invasive way [3]. These techniques include 3D nanostructured electrodes of various shapes and geometry in order to enhance the coupling with the cell membrane. These include 3D nanowire Field Effect Transistors, nanopillars, nanocrowns, nanobranches, nanomushrooms, and nanovolcanos, all of

which enabled spontaneous intracellular access or access via electro/opto-poration[4][5]. Although 3D nano devices are useful for engulfing cells or promoting membrane penetration, their production is complex and expensive. On the other hand, planar non-invasive Micro Electrode Arrays MEAs has been the choice of electrophysiologist when it comes to high throughput recording platform for long term recording. However the signals recorded from planar MEAs also known as extracellular potentials/field potentials is generally a derivative of the actual AP and its signal to noise ratio is rather low. Therefore, with the aim to record the intracellular AP, MEAs have been recently combined with poration techniques such as electroporation or optoporation[6], [7]. In spite of the fact that poration is considered to be minimally invasive to cells, nevertheless their effect on the physiological state of the cell is still questionable[8]. As a result, there is an ongoing research on finding new cell recording platforms that are low cost, easy production that are able to directly and accurately record the AP of cells without the need of any external stimuli.

Recently, carbon-based Electrolyte Gated Field-Effect Transistors (EGFETs) have shown great potential for application in cell recording and stimulation.[9], [10] The intrinsic mechanical property and biocompatibility of such materials make them ideal for interfacing with biological systems. Most carbon-based materials can be easily processed using solution and printing techniques which can greatly decrease the cost and effort required for the fabrication of the devices.

EGFETs are three terminal devices consisting of three electrodes: source, drain, gate and a thin semiconducting film that connects the source and the drain electrodes. An electrolyte is in direct contact with the semiconductor and the immersed gate electrode. The conductivity of the semiconductor is modulated by the potential applied to the gate electrode with respect to the source that is grounded. The working mechanism of EGFETs is governed by the capacitive coupling at the gate/electrolyte and electrolyte/semiconductor interface.[11] Any minute electrical variation occurring at these interfaces is largely transduced by the transistor. Since the capacitance of the double layer is in the range of tens of $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$, these devices normally operate in the less than 1 volt

range and are sensitive to potential variation down to few μVs which makes them ideal to detect small biological signals.[12]

In this work, we will present an *in vitro* recording of the intracellular action potential of human induced Pluripotent Stem Cell derived Cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) using an EGFET. The active material of the EGFET employed consist of solution processed polymer sorted wrapped monochiral semiconducting Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (SWCNTs). Previous work have shown that carbon nanotube EGFETs can be employed for monitoring the growth and proliferation of cells thanks to the high electrical performance and excellent stability.[13], [14]. The presented EGFETs were fabricated via simple cost effective solution processing technique. hiPSC-CMs were cultured directly onto the interconnected network of SWCNTs. Once the cardiomyocytes exhibited spontaneous beating phenomena, the EGFET was turned on at the maximum transconductance and AP recordings were enabled. The shape and duration of the AP recorded trace is quite identical to the cardiac action potential and is similar to the “intracellular potentials” recorded using other reported techniques. The ability to directly record intracellular APs by using a non-invasive planar EGFETs which can be easily produced paves way to many applications that includes low-cost bioelectronics platform for toxicological test and long term cell recording to study chronic diseases.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The schematic of the EGFET is depicted in figure 1(a). The channel of the transistor consists of randomly interconnected network of solution processed semiconducting SWCNTs across the source and drain electrodes. hiPSC-CMs cells are cultured on the EGFETs which were coated with

fibronectin gel to ensure good cell adhesion. The cell medium of the cardiomyocytes act as an electrolyte where the gate electrode made of platinum wire is immersed. An optical image of the EGFET comprising the cardiomyocytes monolayer is shown in figure 1(b). The reported SWCNT EGFETs work as a p-type semiconducting FET. In these devices, when a negative voltage is applied at the gate electrode with respect to the source, cations in the electrolyte diffuses to the interface forming the electrical double layer at the gate/electrolyte and anions drift at electrolyte/semiconductor interfaces resulting in the accumulation of positive charges (holes) in the semiconducting channel of the EGFET. By applying a voltage across the Source-Drain V_{DS} , current I_{DS} is recorded. Typical transfer curve of an EGFET working in electrophysiological condition in the presence of cells, is depicted in figure 1(c).

After about 3 days of culturing, the hiPSC-CMs cells on EGFETs, start to spontaneously contract confirming electrophysiological activity. At this point an electrical characterization of the transistor is performed in order to check the electrical performance of the EGFET. A typical transfer characteristic as shown in figure 1(c) is recorded and from this transfer curve, the transconductance of the transistor is determined as a function of V_{GS} . In order to enable the electrophysiological recording of these cells, the transistor is turned on at its maximum transconductance. In this case, the EGFET was turned on at a fixed $V_{GS} = -0.8\text{ V}$ and V_{DS} at -0.5 V , and the transistor current I_{DS} was recorded over time. As seen in figure 1(d) the recorded I_{DS} (black trace) exhibit a periodic modulation consisting of regular peaks with a particular characteristics. The periodicity of the peaks corresponds to the frequency of the beating cells as observed optically. A modulation of the I_{DS} indicates that the gate voltage applied is indeed not constant. This result reflects that

Figure 1 (a) Schematic of the Electrolyte Gated Field Effect Transistor EGFET coupled with Cardiomyocytes. (b) Optical image of the real device onto which a monolayer of Cardiomyocytes is cultured. (c) Transfer characteristics of the EGFET (d) Spontaneous intracellular recording of the action potential of hiPSCs cardiomyocytes acquired on the transistor current traces of EGFETs as a function of time.

the transistor is transducing the electrical signal of the cardiac cell into an effective change in the applied fixed gate voltage. Another indication confirming this transduction mechanism is the apparent modulation of the leakage gate current I_{GS} (red trace) in figure 1(d). The effective change in V_{GS} is the fraction of the Action Potential that is being transduced by the EGFET. A rough estimation can be achieved by using the formula $V_{AP} = \Delta I_{DS}/g_m$ where g_m is the transconductance of the transistor at the applied V_{GS} . The estimated amplitude ranges between 1 and 3 mV, a considerable fraction of AP amplitude, and comparable to recently reported works that employ electro[15] or optoporation[16].

III. CONCLUSION

To conclude, we have demonstrated that an EGFET based on solution processed semiconducting SWCNT can directly record the Action Potential of Cardiomyocytes. This is the first reported spontaneous recording of intracellular-like signals using a planar transistor technology. The optimal coupling between the channel of the EGFET and the cells allows the recording of a good fraction of the APs of about 1-3 mV. EGFETs were produced with solution processed active materials and using cost-effective fabrication methods such as spin-coating. Exploiting these materials and techniques could lead to flexible large-area biosensor arrays for mapping and monitoring the activity of electrogenic cell cultures, in vivo biomedical applications, or disposable devices for drug testing.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Device fabrication

Transistor arrays consisting of interdigitated source-drain electrodes with channel length of 3 μm and channel width of 146 μm and 64 μm were fabricated and patterned on a glass substrate using mask-less reverse lithography process (AZ5214 photoresist using MLA100 Heidelberg mask-less aligner) followed by thermal evaporation of chromium (2 nm)/gold (15 nm) and lift-off in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. Gold electrodes were subjected to 3 min of oxygen plasma treatment at 100 W prior to the semiconductor coating. Semiconducting SWCNTs dispersion made in toluene (concentration of (6,5) SWCNTs of 18 mg L⁻¹, corresponding to an optical density of 10 cm⁻¹ at the E11 absorption peak) was spincoated on the chip. Three passes of spincoating were done in nitrogen glovebox where a 1 min annealing at 100 C is followed after each pass. Spincoated semiconductor layer was then rinsed with tetrahydrofuran, isopropanol and dried with a nitrogen flux. To passivate Source and drain electrodes, a film of inkjet-printed biocompatible insulator (SU8 – TF6001 MicroChem) was printed.

Characterization of EGFETs and Cell Recording

The electrical performance of the SWCNT EGFETs was measured using cell medium (iCell Cardiomyocytes Maintenance Medium) as an electrolyte and platinum wire as the gate electrode for applying the gate bias. To check the electrical performance of the transistor, a transfer curve is acquired using Agilent 2912B source meter. Gate voltage V_{GS} is swept from +0.2 V to -0.8 V, keeping the V_{DS} constant at -0.5 V. For bioelectronics recording, V_{GS} is then fixed at a bias point where the EGFET has maximum transconductance g_m . Keeping the V_{DS} constant at -0.5V, I_{DS} is recorded over time. The data obtained is then post processed by using the

asymmetric baseline smoothing to eliminate the drift in the current. No other filter is applied in the raw data acquired. After each recording, an IV transfer curve is taken in order to check the stability of the device.

Cell culture on the EGFETs

Human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) were purchased from Cellular Dynamics International (CDI). hiPSC-CMs were plated directly on EGFETs (30,000 cells for device) coated with fibronectin (Corning) for 1 hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator. EGFETs were previously sterilized in 70% ethanol for 30 min followed by three washes with sterile water. The cells were cultured on the devices and electrophysiological recordings were performed 10-14 days after plating according to the specifications of CDI.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Orvos *et al.*, "Evaluation of Possible Proarrhythmic Potency: Comparison of the Effect of Dofetilide, Cisapride, Sotalol, Terfenadine, and Verapamil on hERG and Native IKr Currents and on Cardiac Action Potential," *Toxicol. Sci.*, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfy299>.
- [2] B. Sakman and E. Neher, "PATCH CLAMP TECHNIQUES FOR STUDYING IONIC CHANNELS IN EXCITABLE MEMBRANES," *Ann. Rev. Physiol.*, vol. 46, 1984.
- [3] P. B. Kruskal, Z. Jiang, T. Gao, and C. M. Lieber, "Beyond the patch clamp: Nanotechnologies for intracellular recording," *Neuron*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 21–24, 2015, doi: [10.1016/j.neuron.2015.01.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.01.004).
- [4] Y. Zhao, S. S. You, A. Zhang, J. H. Lee, J. Huang, and C. M. Lieber, "Scalable ultrasmall three-dimensional nanowire transistor probes for intracellular recording," *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 14, no. 8, pp. 783–790, 2019, doi: [10.1038/s41565-019-0478-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-019-0478-y).
- [5] M. Dipalo *et al.*, "Plasmonic meta-electrodes allow intracellular recordings at network level on high-density CMOS-multi-electrode arrays," *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 965–971, 2018, doi: [10.1038/s41565-018-0222-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-018-0222-z).
- [6] J. Lee *et al.*, "Repeated and On-Demand Intracellular Recordings of Cardiomyocytes Derived from Human-Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells," *ACS Sensors*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 3181–3191, 2022, doi: [10.1021/acssensors.2c01678](https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.2c01678).
- [7] G. Melle *et al.*, "Intracellular Recording of Human Cardiac Action Potentials on Market-Available Multielectrode Array Platforms," *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.*, vol. 8, no. February, pp. 1–10, 2020, doi: [10.3389/fbioe.2020.00066](https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00066).
- [8] V. V. Fedorov, V. P. Nikolski, and I. R. Efimov, "Effect of electroporation on cardiac electrophysiology.," *Methods Mol. Biol.*, vol. 423, pp. 433–448, 2008, doi: [10.1007/978-1-59745-194-9_34](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-59745-194-9_34).
- [9] A. Kyndiah *et al.*, "Bioelectronic Recordings of Cardiomyocytes with Accumulation Mode Electrolyte Gated Organic Field Effect Transistors," *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, vol. 150, no. August 2019, p. 111844, 2020, doi: [10.1016/j.bios.2019.111844](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.111844).
- [10] A. Campana, T. Cramer, D. T. Simon, M. Berggren, and F. Biscarini, "Electrocardiographic recording with conformable organic electrochemical transistor fabricated on resorbable bioscaffold," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 26, no. 23, pp. 3874–3878, 2014, doi: [10.1002/adma.201400263](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201400263).
- [11] F. Torricelli *et al.*, "Electrolyte-gated transistors for enhanced performance bioelectronics," *Nat. Rev. Methods Prim.*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2021, doi: [10.1038/s43586-021-00065-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-021-00065-8).
- [12] T. Cramer, A. Kyndiah, M. Murgia, F. Leonardi, S. Casalini, and F. Biscarini, "Double layer capacitance measured by organic field effect transistor operated in water," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 100, no. 14, p. 143302, Apr. 2012, doi: [10.1063/1.3699218](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3699218).
- [13] F. Scuratti *et al.*, "Real-Time Monitoring of Cellular Cultures with Electrolyte-Gated Carbon Nanotube Transistors," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 11, no. 41, pp. 37966–37972, 2019, doi: [10.1021/acsami.9b11383](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b11383).
- [14] A. Molazemhosseini, F. A. Viola, F. J. Berger, N. F. Zorn, J. Zaumseil, and M. Caironi, "A Rapidly Stabilizing Water-Gated Field-Effect Transistor Based on Printed Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes for Biosensing Applications," *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 3106–3113, 2021, doi: [10.1021/acsaelm.1c00332](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.1c00332).
- [15] Y. Jimbo *et al.*, "An organic transistor matrix for multipoint intracellular action potential recording," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, vol. 118, no. 39, pp. 1–8, 2021, doi: [10.1073/pnas.2022300118](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2022300118).
- [16] M. Dipalo *et al.*, "Intracellular action potential recordings from cardiomyocytes by ultrafast pulsed laser irradiation of fuzzy graphene microelectrodes," *Sci. Adv.*, vol. 7, no. 15, pp. 1–10, 2021, doi: [10.1126/SCIADV.ABD5175](https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIADV.ABD5175).